

THE USE OF CULTURALLY RELEVANT TEXT FOR STUDENTS' READING MOTIVATION

¹Hoang Thi Huyen Trang; ²Tran Thi Phuong

School of Foreign Languages, Thai Nguyen University

Email: ¹hoangtrang.sfl@tnu.edu.vn; ²tranphuong.sfl@tnu.edu.vn

ABSTRACT

Reading is one of the most important language skills for building up learners' second language competence and performance. Much research has been conducted on reading proficiency in order to find ways to develop learners' second language acquisitions. With the same purpose, this study investigates into the uses of culturally relevant texts on EFL/ESL learners' reading motivation and suggests using culturally relevant texts (CRTs) as materials for motivating learners in reading courses (intensively and extensively). The study clarifies some definitions of key concepts of reading, culturally relevant texts, and reading motivation. It highlights the roles of cultural knowledge on learners' reading competence and provides the criteria that can be used to select a culturally relevant text for reading classrooms.

Key words: Reading motivation, background knowledge, culturally relevant texts, reading comprehension

1 INTRODUCTION

Mikulecky and Jeffries (2004) mentioned that reading is one of the important ways to improve general language skills in English. They elaborated that reading help learners learn to think in English, enlarge their English vocabulary bank, and improve their writing skills. In fact, written texts serve various pedagogical purposes. Good reading texts provide good models for writing and provide opportunities to introduce new topics, to stimulate discussion and to study language. However, a large number of ESL learners have certain difficulties with English reading which might affect their attitudes towards reading in English (Mede, 2010).

In Vietnam, English reading skill has been found to be challenging for Vietnamese students as well. Hang (2009) found that Vietnamese learners experienced considerable difficulties with reading as they found Vietnamese learners have not developed reading skills as such as using context clues or locating main ideas. She believes that there are some reasons explaining students' English reading weaknesses. Many students complained that they have had difficulty in reading English texts because they lack vocabulary to understand the text. More importantly, students lack motivation in reading classes. Students are observed to show their little or no interest in reading activities. They are found sleeping, making noises or sitting silently in the classes. Most students rarely volunteer to perform in front of the class. In addition, a large

number of reading texts overwhelms them. Consequently, students seem to lack interests in exploring information or they are demotivated to read in English. From teaching experiences of the researcher and other teachers of English, a lack of motivation is believed to be a very important factor that causes Vietnamese students of English difficulties in reading.

The aim of this article is first to describe what reading motivation primarily is and then to look at how culturally relevant texts help improve students' reading motivation

2 WHAT IS READING MOTIVATION?

It is common knowledge that motivation is vast and complicated subject encompassing many theories. Motivation is thought to be important and inevitable in most fields, without which one is difficult to succeed. Most definitions of motivation reflect that motivation is an internal state or condition that serves to activate or energize behavior and give it direction. Kleinginna & Kleinginna (1981) defines motivation as "a desire or want that energizes and directs goal-oriented behavior" (p. 212). Similarly, Brown (1994) indicates that "motivation is some kinds of internal drive which pushes someone to do things in order to achieve something." Motivation is also suggested by Woolfolk (2000) as "an internal state that arouses, directs and maintains behavior". Harmer (1991) explains the meaning of motivation as the "internal drive" that "encourage[s] somebody to pursue a course of actions". Based on his observation, for example, when a student becomes conscious of a goal that is something they desire to achieve and if s/he finds it really attractive, s/he will do whatever needed under any circumstances to reach that goal. In other words, if we think that our goal is worth doing and attractive for us, then we will find ways to reach that goal; this is called "the action driven by motivation".

Martin (2008) depicted motivation and engagement as the determiners for knowledge that students can learn from school and as the measurement of the energy that students put into their learning. According to Wigfield and Guthrie (2000), motivation is the will, determination, desire, and purposes to get involved in a certain task. It is often defined concerning the beliefs, values, and goals that a person has for an activity.

3 ROLES OF READING MOTIVATION

Motivation plays a critical role in raising students' reading skills (Wigfield & Guthrie, 2000). They defined motivation to read as "the individual's personal goal, values and beliefs with regard to the topics, process, and outcomes of reading" (p.405). As it has been found to be one of the factors that affect the reading ability, Wang, Guthrie, Tonks and Parnacevic (2004) found that motivated readers choose to engage in reading activities more frequently than those with low motivation. With the increase in reading practice, the learners in the study improved their comprehension ability.

Students need to have motivation and become engaged with learning activities in order to achieve success in reading and writing. Without reading motivation, students will benefit less from

learning reading (Brozo & Flynt, 2008). In other words, lack of motivation will push students away from literacy competence and build up a learning resistance. Irvin, Meltzer, and Dukes (2007) indicated that students would not highly engage with writing and reading activities, if the topic does not convey something important to their daily communication; or it is not of their interests; or the students do not have enough reason to participate. Therefore, before designing reading and writing activities and assignments in the classroom, teachers need to understand the diversity, competency and the insights in the out-of-school literacy experiences of students (Alvermann & Moore, 1991; Smith & Wilhelm, 2004). It is necessary for teachers to bear in mind the connection between the classroom activities with students’ daily lives outside schools. In doing so, teachers have motivated students in engaging with literacy learning.

4 THE TEXT: FACTOR INFLUENCING READING MOTIVATION

Instead of looking at a myriad of factors that can affect student motivation within the school context, Renandya (2015) focus on classroom specific factors that teachers are most familiar with and which they can make the most impacts on, for instance, the classroom environment, our behavior and actions in the classroom, our relationship with the students, the way we teach in class, and how we structure our lessons, and the way we assess our students. These classroom specific factors are referred to as the 5 Ts of motivation as shown in Figure 1 below:

Figure 2: The 5 Ts of Motivation (Adapted from Renandya, 2015, p.181)

This study finds way to explore more deeply in the role of the Text as one factor that contributes to student’s reading intrinsic motivation since sources of intrinsic motivation include positive reading experiences, books regarded as pleasurable, realizing the personal importance of reading, and interest in the topic read (Becker, McElvany and Kortenbruck, 2010).

According to Renandya (2015),since the Text is given the important role of instructional materials in the language learning process, it is essential that the materials we use are interesting and motivating. Renandya (2015) shows that “not much learning can occur if the materials are linguistically, cognitively and affectively unappealing to the learners” (p.184). The following list of questions can be used to gauge the interest level of the instructional materials we use (Renandya, 2015, p.185):

- *“Are the materials pitched at the right linguistic levels, not too easy and not too demanding?”*
 - *Do the materials contain language items that attract students’ attention?*
 - *Are the contents appropriate for the students you are teaching?*
- *Do the materials help the learners make personally meaningful connections with their own lives?*
 - *Do the materials help the learners make connections with the lives of the people in their surrounding?*
- *Do the materials provide positive learning experiences and promote students’ self-esteem and self-confidence?*
- *Do the materials provide ample opportunity for students to learn what they really need or want to learn?*
 - *Are the materials emotionally stimulating and engaging?”*

The affective dimension of course materials is particularly important in language learning. ELT materials development experts such as Tomlinson and Masuhara (2004) contend that “materials should engage the emotions of the learner. Laughter, joy, excitement, sorrow and anger can promote learning; neutrality cannot” (p. 6). This type of materials allows learners to process the contents and language of the materials at a much deeper level, resulting in the kind of learning that is durable and long lasting. If the reading material is interesting and relevant to the students, it will motivate them to read more. Reading materials should have suitable contents, which means that the suitable texts will tell students things they do not know, introduce to them new and relevant ideas and suit their reading levels. Secondly, reading material’s language items such as vocabulary and grammatical structures may have impacts on students’ motivation. Through the texts, students can understand the way the others feel or think and make them read for themselves.

Many researchers while studying this field find the problem in text selection (Ebe, 2010) that texts that are used to assess the reading proficiency of EFL/ESL learners are not culturally relevant for the students who read them. Often a writer will assume that the target reader has the relevant background knowledge to read and make meanings out of the text; therefore, the writer will leave certain facts out or unstated. However, this creates problems when the writer and readers do not share the same relevant background knowledge (Berardo, 2006). This problem is found in many nations where ESL/EFL holds an important place in education. One example is found in Taiwan, where most English texts that Taiwanese students read are narrative or expository passages; thus, many students cannot interact with the context and they cannot learn the whole picture of the reading passages (Weng, 2012).

The same situation happens in China where reading courses are intended to develop general reading skills, the ability to read quickly and an ability to grasp main meaning. As a result, many students cope with distasteful job assignments in which little knowledge of English is actually required, and quickly lose their interest in English (Stuart, 1990). Another example is

in Ebe (2010)'s research in which Ebe told her story about her students in New York, who came from the flat deserts of Northern Mexico and had to struggle to read texts about children climbing mountains and finding caves with waterfalls. She also gave the familiar situations of her college in Hong Kong that the students had difficulties in reading the texts not only because they are not proficient in English, but also because they lack the background knowledge to connect to the reading texts.

5 WHAT IS CRTS?

Culturally relevant texts (CRTs) are literary texts that depict aspects of learner's culture such as ways of life, ways of dressing, food, artifacts and others, which are unique to the learners' culture and are familiar to them (Davoudi & Ramezani, 2014). Brock (1990) explains that CRTs are texts that include subject matters, contexts, cultural assumptions, circumstances, characters, language, and historical references that are recognizable to the second language readers. In simple words, CRTs are those that readers can connect to (Freeman & Freeman, 2004) and can draw on their background knowledge and experiences to make meanings (Erten & Razi, 2009).

According to Alanís (2007), CRTs can be defined as texts which contain events or information that is within children's experience, and which draws on their background and culture. CRTs help students understand who they are and where they come from because they connect to their lives, not just to their cultural heritage, and such connection facilitates their comprehension (Alanís, 2007; Freeman & Freeman, 2004).

Many studies have shown that the reading comprehension (Brozo, Valerio & Salazar, 1996; Gatbonton & Tucker, 1971,) and responses (Jimenez & Gamez, 1996) of ESL learners showed a marked improvement when reading culturally relevant texts in comparison to culturally unfamiliar ones. The learners' ability to identify with and immerse in the culture that is portrayed in the text enhances their engagement and understanding of it. This familiarity for the ESL learners may overcome some of the linguistic complexity – syntactic or vocabulary of such texts. Brock (1990) emphasizes that linguistic complexity should be less of a concern than cultural familiarity when choosing literature texts for the use of ESL learners.

A number of studies show that teachers who exhibit culturally relevant instruction promotes high achievement among students (Alanís, 2007) by: bridge the gap between the school and the world of the student; provide positive perspectives on parents and families; demonstrate cultural sensitivity; use active teaching methods; provide culturally mediated instruction.

6 ROLES CRTS IN STUDENT'S READING MOTIVATION

Introducing CRTs allows students to see their cultures represented in the school environment. This, in turn, has led to successful engagement in reading, as culturally relevant books “engage the learner in the concepts being taught on a more meaningful and personal level; and they create an inclusive learning environment” (Purnell, Ali, Begum & Carter, 2007, p. 421). Sims (1983)

conducted a landmark study of an African American reader reading African American children's books. The results showed that the CRTs initiated the reader's interest and engagement in the stories. Since then, many other studies have been conducted and accordingly have demonstrated support for Sims' argument, inviting students to explore their community, history and heritage and therefore to value where they come from and who they are.

A strong influence of the CRTs on learners' reading comprehension has been well documented in literature. Many researchers implemented CRTs on their reading classrooms with different methodologies and found that CRTs have good impacts on developing reading comprehension ability of students at different levels and ages. They found that the use of these books that are culturally relevant validated the culture and life experiences of the participant readers. Validating and celebrating students' backgrounds and cultural experiences can often lead to reading engagement and increased reading proficiency.

Fredricks (2012) initiated critical literature circles in which a program drew from critical literacy and culturally relevant pedagogy, on his adult students in Tajikistan. In this program, students worked together in small, peer-led discussion groups whose members had chosen to read the same reading texts about their own historical, cultural and social issues and then shared opinions about what they had read in an educational setting. The program came up with excellent outcomes in which readers developed personal responses to literature, could express their views on texts in relation to their own life experiences, beliefs and values, and had an opportunity for enjoyable L2 reading experiences. "Many members reported enjoying reading texts they had chosen rather than those that they were forced to read for course" (Fredricks, 2012, p.498).

The interaction between CRTs and language proficiency level in EFL learner's reading comprehension was investigated through a quantitative method conducted by Weng (2012). Four reading tests, in which four reading texts of different backgrounds were chosen, were designed to examine the effect of background knowledge on reading comprehension. The participants, who came from six classes of university freshmen in Taiwan, had to read four different texts and then answered 20 follow-up questions. The findings of the study indicated that participants got higher grades in their topic familiar readings than topic unfamiliar readings and topic familiarity was perceived as being more important by participants at lower language proficiency levels.

Another reading method was used by participants coming from an urban elementary school in the United States of America by Ebe (2010). Each participant was asked to read and retell two third-grade stories which were different in the content but identical in the level of difficulty. After analyzing the results, the researcher found that students were more proficient in their reading of the story they identified as being more culturally relevant. The connections seen in these studies between the CRTs and reading proficiency indicate that teachers can help support the reading development of their EFL/ESL learners by considering cultural relevance when selecting texts as reading materials (Ebe, 2010).

In her case study, Packard (2001) used culturally relevant literature and shared reading strategies to help her Chinese mother become interested in reading. As time went by, the texts by Asian or Asian American authors featuring Asian or Asian American characters not only engaged the mother but also initiated conversations over family history between the mother and daughter. Packard (2001) was noticing much progress in her mother's reading which was the first time that she had read so much in English. During that time, Packard also realized that it was the first time she knew so much about the Chinese part of herself. Implications of Packard's study indicated the potential benefits of using CRTs to create family literacy programs and therefore to help immigrant students to fill the intergenerational, intercultural gap with parents in terms of language and traditions.

In another study conducted by Freeman (2004), the researcher reported on her research conducted with students at secondary schools Arizona in which miscue analysis was used to compare students' reading of a culturally relevant book with their reading of another book that had little cultural relevance. The findings of the study revealed that students made higher quality miscues and produced better retellings with the culturally relevant story. It was reported in the research that students can more easily construct meaning from a text that contains familiar elements because their background knowledge helps them make predictions and inferences about the story. Freeman (2004) also stated that another important reason for using culturally relevant texts is that they help students understand who they are. Using culturally relevant books is one way to ensure that students' linguistic and cultural backgrounds are represented in the curriculum.

Later, Feger (2006) demonstrated the effects of the implementation of CRTs on reading engagement. As a classroom teacher, Feger observed that textbooks focusing on grammar helped her 9th and 10th grade ELL (English Language Learning) students to master a sufficient command of English grammar to participate in classroom lessons. However, she also realized that the books did little to engage her students, much less develop their literacy. When recognizing that her students' cultural diversity determined their opportunities for success in literacy, Feger led her students to read stories depicting immigrant children and to share their responses to the stories in dialogue journals. Students' reflection and reaction continuously observed by the teacher showed that CRTs transformed the level of engagement in reading for the English language learners in her class and their scores on the high-stakes test improved.

A year later, Alanis (2007) also conducted a study on elementary students in a remote section of the Texas/Mexico border where a Spanish/English dual-language education program was implemented with attempt to develop children's identities with culturally responsive pedagogy. One crucial strategy is the use of culturally relevant texts, which can be defined as texts containing events or information that is within children's experience, and which draws on their background and culture. CRTs and books were carefully chosen based on Cultural Relevance Rubrics. Results concluded from observation and interviews showed that children's literature that shares the experiences, contributions, and perspectives of various cultural groups can help young children develop a sense of belonging and identity. And using CRTs is one way to provide a

crucial link between prior knowledge and reading comprehension texts since students are intrinsically motivated to read.

More recently, another study on CRTs was conducted by Ebe (2010). The nine third-grade ELLs who participated in this study came from an urban elementary school located in a large Northeastern city in the United States that had a total of 45 third grade ELL students. All of the students were invited to participate in the study, and nine children and their parents responded. The nine participants included ELLs who came from the Caribbean, Mexico, and Central America. Each participant was asked to read and retell two third grade stories from a commercial assessment kit which identified them as being at the same reading assessment level. While the stories have approximately the same number of words, despite their similarities, they appear to differ in their degree of cultural relevance. The student's reading was assessed using scoring assessment which showed that the more engaged students are with CRTs; the more developed their reading skills may become.

To conclude, the prior knowledge a reader brings to a text improves reading comprehension and therefore the pleasure in reading. Subject knowledge, language knowledge, world knowledge and text type knowledge are all parts of the plans that readers bring to the act of reading. Bamford and Day (1998) cite Gabe's statement that "the more reading done, of the greatest informational variety and range of purposes, the quicker the reader will achieve... the capacity for creating, refining, and connecting diverse arrays of cognitive schemata." (p. 36) In other words, when teachers use CRTs, students have a better understanding of the books and, as a result, they become more engaged in their reading. Their enjoyment and interest increase, and they become motivated to read more (Alanís, 2007; Ebe, 2010).

7 CRITERIA TO SELECT CRTS

While there are many studies highlighting the positive influences of CRTs on learners' reading comprehension ability, the question many teachers may ask is what makes a text culturally relevant (Ebe, 2010). Although a wide range of books is available, determining cultural relevance should go beyond the nationality or ethnicity of the main character and include a number of other factors (Freeman & Freeman, 2004).

Building on Goodman's (1982) work, a rubric that can be used as a text selection tool to help identify CRTs was later developed (Ebe, 2010; Freeman & Freeman, 2004). The rubric, as can be seen from Figure 1, was refined to include a set of questions around the seven factors identified earlier by Goodman (1982). Teachers and students can consider eight factors as they choose texts using this rubric, namely 1) the ethnicity of the characters, 2) the setting, 3) the year the story takes place, 4) age of the characters, 5) gender of the characters, 6) the language or dialect used in the story, 7) the genre and exposure to this type of text, and 8) the reader's background experiences. Using a five point Likert scale, teachers or readers can rate each question on the rubric with possible responses ranging from a "1" indicating no connection ("not at all like us" or

irrelevance) to a “5” showing a very close connection to the particular aspect of culture (“just like us” or relevance).

Cultural Relevance Rubric				
a. Are the characters in the story like you and your family?				
<i>Just like us</i> <i>Not at all like us</i>				
5	4	3	2	1
b. Have you ever lived in or visited places like those in the story?				
<i>Yes</i> <i>No</i>				
5	4	3	2	1
c. Could this story take place this year?				
<i>Yes</i> <i>No</i>				
5	4	3	2	1
d. How close do you think the main characters are to you in age?				
<i>Very close</i> <i>Not close at all</i>				
5	4	3	2	1
e. Does the story have main characters who are boys (for boy readers)/girls (for girl readers)?				
<i>Yes</i> <i>No</i>				
5	4	3	2	1
f. Do the characters talk like you and your family?				
<i>Yes</i> <i>No</i>				
5	4	3	2	1
g. How often do you read stories like this one?				
<i>Often</i> <i>Never</i>				
5	4	3	2	1
h. Have you ever had an experience like one described in this story?				
<i>Yes</i> <i>No</i>				
5	4	3	2	1

Figure 1: Cultural Relevance Rubrics (Ebe, 2010, p.198)

8 CONCLUSION

This study has presented evidence on a strong relationship between CRTs and intrinsic reading motivation of intermediate learners. CRTs reading can increase not only students’ motivation but also promote student’s reading comprehension.

In conclusion, the results from the previous researches expose the natural impact of culturally relevant texts on second language reading comprehension and hence, improving students’ reading motivation. CRTs have been exactly instrumental in connecting the contextual meanings with EFL/ESL readers’ comprehension. It is important to note that different books are culturally

relevant for different readers and identifying texts that are relevant for a reader for all eight factors is a difficult work. However, finding texts with some cultural relevance for the reader is supportive. In other words, not every text is necessarily relevant to readers' cultural background knowledge but at least some of the texts EFL/ESL learners are provided should be culturally relevant.

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